

THE PLACE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN MODERN EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses some aspects of inclusive education at the stage of modernization of the modern educational process and its methodological support in the basic education system. Recommendations for the modern use of the grant program were also taken into account and developed.

Introduction. Nowadays, the education system is developing more and more. As a result, all conditions are created for the active learning of physically weak children in the higher education system. The requirement of today is the training of spiritually mature personnel. Therefore, we consider inclusive education as a process of general education development, which implies the possibility of education for everyone, including children with special needs.

Research materials and methods. With the development of this type of education, effective work is being carried out in the great countries of the world. In particular, the leaders in this regard are scientists from Russia, Great Britain, the USA, China and many other countries. In the development of inclusive education, Russian scientists Dityatkina I.A., Kirichenko S., Buchilova I.A., Berdysheva I.A., Glukhova O.A., Lekhanova O.A. and many other scientists made great contributions to the development of this education.

Inclusive education for children with disabilities is a principled new perspective, a basic and comprehensive education. Therefore, at the stage of modernization of the modern education process, taking into account all the resources aimed at ensuring the equal rights of students, developing the skills necessary for communication in all children, laying the foundations of inclusive education without disruptions and interruptions, and participation of kindergarten, school, university employees in all issues and possible risks in its implementation, organization of the educational process, which consists of a mass transition to inclusive education according to a single plan and principles consists of. Additionally, gifted and gifted children with disabilities need to be supported rather than ignored. Personal dignity, the right to communication, diversity of education, the context of real relationships - these are the basic principles of inclusive education, which has equal development conditions for all its participants, regardless of abilities and capabilities. create a tolerant society.

In order for children with disabilities to more successfully master the general education program, it is necessary to make changes in the ways of providing the information necessary to the student in each student's individual plan. This means that disabled children must be provided with special conditions compared to their classmates: changing the form of the assignment, deadline, etc.

Educational programs in the traditional education system are represented by a set of textbooks that reflect a certain amount of knowledge. New information delivery technologies make it possible to adapt educational programs to the interests and capabilities of students. The inclusive education system should also be designed in a convenient and quality manner for educational needs in accordance with the curriculum, using simple and effective ways for students to understand. Children with disabilities need special educational services. They have difficulty perceiving, processing and using information. In many ways, this prevents them from adapting to society.

Research result. An effective way to educate such children is to organize distance learning. Distance education gives children the opportunity to receive a quality education and communicate with peers regardless of the place of study, which contributes to adaptation in society. Having learned to use a computer, a child will acquire professional skills that will provide him with a decent life and work in the future. The distance education system allows you to freely express your individual opinion and discover your free thinking skills.

In addition, distance education serves to ensure high-quality training of students, develop independence in cognitive activity, and increase the prestige of this type of education among students and their parents. At the same time, training is individual: each child studies according to a schedule convenient for him and at a pace convenient for him. It should be noted that inclusive education is effective only if actions are provided aimed at helping the child in the process of understanding educational material.

Inclusive education also requires mandatory high-quality and regular cooperation of support system specialists with specialists in general and special education, as well as the organization of constant exchange of information between specialists and families, or includes the connection of interests of all participants in the educational process, including children with disabilities. The main thing in the inclusive education of a child with disabilities is to gain social and educational experience with peers. Only by satisfying the special educational needs of such a child can the path to general education be opened for him [3].

The development of life skills of a disabled child is of particular importance. A component of life competence is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities that a child needs in everyday life. If the acquisition of knowledge, skills and competencies is aimed mainly at ensuring their implementation in the future, then life competence ensures the development of relationships with the environment at the moment [4]. Therefore, the idea of inclusive education is currently considered as one of the components of the modernization of the modern educational process, as a step towards creating a society that allows any child to study, regardless of age, abilities and disabilities. Solving these problems is a priority for the state [5,6].

Conclusion. The place of inclusive education in the modern education system is increasing, the main reason being to meet the vocational and educational needs of students with disabilities. In this regard, a conclusion was made about the possibility of distance education and its advantages were considered.

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